

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in Italy

Country report

Laurence Lessard-Phillips
Giulia Garofalo Geymonat

March 2026

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the European Union under Grant Number 101094373. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
2. About the Survey	5
2.1. Development and methodology	5
2.2. Target population, sample and fieldwork	5
2.3. Data analysis	5
2.4. Survey respondents' main characteristics	6
3. Views toward immigration	7
4. Main Results	9
4.1. Knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants	10
4.1.1. Scale and level of concern	10
4.1.2. Becoming 'irregular': testing scenarios	11
4.2. Irregular migrant and work: sectors & overall feelings	15
4.3. Attitudes	16
4.3.1. Hiring choice	16
4.3.2. Perceptions of integration and settlement	21
5. Conclusion	27
6. References	29
Appendices	31

Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of the I-CLAIM survey on public perceptions of irregular migration, conducted in Italy in February 2025 with a nationally representative sample of 1,077 adults. The survey offers novel empirical insights into public understandings of irregular migration in Italy, including how it is defined, the extent of public knowledge, and prevailing attitudes toward irregular migrants, particularly in relation to work.

The findings point to substantial knowledge deficits. A majority of respondents markedly overestimated the proportion of irregular migrants within the foreign-born population. While existing estimates indicate that irregular migrants represent 9.4% of the foreign-born population, respondents consistently reported significantly higher figures. This tendency was especially pronounced among older individuals and those with right-leaning political orientations, although it was also evident among younger respondents and voters of the Partito Democratico.

Knowledge gaps were also apparent in relation to pathways into irregular status. When asked about the processes through which irregularity arises, respondents predominantly associated irregular status with unauthorised border crossings and pending asylum applications, reflecting dominant media and political framings. In contrast, fewer respondents identified routine administrative mechanisms—such as visa overstaying or the loss of residence status following employment changes—which play a central role in the production of irregularity within the Italian context.

Perceptions of irregular migrants and employment were characterised by ambivalence. Respondents identified sectors such as agriculture, construction, cleaning, care work (including childcare and eldercare), food delivery, and hospitality as key areas of irregular employment. In open-ended responses, additional sectors such as street-based vending and sex work were also mentioned.

In hiring experiments, they revealed a pragmatic orientation: respondents tended to favour candidates with longer residence in Italy, positive recommendations, and established family ties in the country, even where irregular status was implied. These preferences, however, were shaped by racialised hierarchies, with candidates from Morocco being less favourably evaluated compared to those from Peru and Ukraine, and women less favourably viewed when they do not have their family and friends in Italy.

Perceptions of integration were primarily shaped by indicators of social embeddedness, notably proficiency in the Italian language and the presence of family and social networks in Italy. Overall, respondents reported relatively low levels of social distance in workplace settings, and even lower levels in commercial and domestic contexts—particularly significant given the prevalence of irregular migrant domestic and care work in private households in Italy.

In sum, the survey demonstrates that public understandings of irregular migration in Italy are fragmented, uneven, and frequently misaligned with empirical realities. Attitudes reflect a combination of suspicion and pragmatism, alongside a degree of openness toward markers of social integration and belonging. These findings underscore the need to address both widespread misperceptions and the broader narrative frameworks that shape public discourse on irregular migration.

1. Introduction

Irregular migration can be defined as a situation where foreign nationals residing within a given country lack a valid legal residence status due to a range of circumstances. Public knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants is limited.

Despite its policy relevance, public knowledge and attitudes concerning irregular migration and irregular migrants remain limited. This report seeks to contribute to addressing this evidentiary gap by presenting the main findings of an online survey conducted in February 2025 on public perceptions of irregular migration among the Italian population.

The survey forms part of the Horizon Europe-funded project “*Improving the living and labour conditions of irregularised migrant households in Europe*” (I-CLAIM), and focuses on public understandings of irregular migration in general, with particular emphasis on its intersections with work and employment. The analysis follows a harmonised framework and draws on the methodological blueprint developed in the UK report (Lessard-Phillips and Sigona, 2025).

This report builds upon prior research (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025) examining the narrative construction of migrant irregularity in Italy across three key domains: media, politics, and civil society. That work analysed how different actors shape public discourse on irregular migration, with particular attention to the intersections of employment, gender, race, and family-related representations.

Findings from this earlier research highlighted that public narratives around irregular migration are both constructed and contested across these media, political and civil society. They also revealed a significant disjunction between dominant representations—often reductive and focused on highly visible phenomena such as Mediterranean crossings, rescue operations, criminalisation, and severe labour exploitation in agriculture—and the broader, more complex realities of irregular migration, including its structural drivers and governance mechanisms, which remain largely obscured.

Drawing on these insights, as well as on the concept of the ‘irregularity assemblage’ (Sigona and van Liempt 2025, Sigona et al., 2021), the survey is informed by an understanding of irregularity not as a fixed status, but as a dynamic position vis-à-vis the state co-constructed at the intersection of different regulatory frameworks (Gonzales et al., 2019) encompassing not only migrants without a residence permit, but migrants increasingly at risk of irregularisation due to structural features of the immigration system (Palumbo 2026, Palumbo and Marchetti 2024).

Within this framework, the I-CLAIM survey investigates how the Italian public defines irregular migrants, the meanings attributed to this categorisation, and the implications of these perceptions for attitudes and responses toward irregular migrants.

The survey contributes to the growing body of evidence on irregular migration by combining ‘traditional’ survey questions with experimental approaches, which have become increasingly prominent in the study of public attitudes (Sobolewska & Lessard-Phillips, 2024). In this report, we draw on these data to address two central research questions:

- What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants?
- What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work?

Before turning to these questions, the following section provides an overview of the survey design and sample characteristics.

2. About the Survey

2.1. Development and methodology

The I-CLAIM survey was designed to assess public perceptions of, and attitudes toward, irregularity among the general population in Italy. To achieve this objective, an online survey was administered by YouGov. The instrument combined ‘traditional’ survey questions with survey experiments¹, enabling the collection of data on public opinion regarding irregular migration and irregular migrants, as well as broader attitudes toward immigration and relevant socio-demographic characteristics.

The questionnaire was developed collaboratively within the I-CLAIM consortium through a series of workshops and structured discussions. It comprised six thematic sections and a total of 25 questions (see Table A.1 in the Appendix for an overview). Prior to fieldwork, the survey instrument underwent testing and piloting with a small group of respondents to ensure clarity and reliability. In addition to survey responses, the final dataset incorporated demographic information drawn from YouGov’s panel of registered users (Abraham, 2025).

2.2. Target population, sample and fieldwork

The survey targeted the adult population residing in Italy, with the objective of obtaining responses from a minimum of 1,000 participants. Respondents were selected from YouGov’s panel of registered users through a process of ‘targeted quota sampling’. This approach aimed to ensure that the sample closely approximated the composition of the Italian population.

To enhance representativeness, YouGov applied sampling quotas and weighting procedures based on a range of characteristics, including age, gender, level of education, vote in the 2022 National Election, region of residence, location (urban/rural), and level of political interest. Data collection took place between 6th and 12th of February 2025. A total of 1,077 completed responses were obtained during this period.

2.3. Data analysis

The statistical analyses were conducted using Stata. All data were examined using the most appropriate analytical techniques for each research question, applying the provided sampling weights throughout. For categorical variables, we relied on percentage frequency distributions for both univariate and bivariate analyses, supported by chi-squared and difference in proportion tests to assess potential associations. All reported percentages are based on a minimum of five respondents. For continuous variables, we calculated means and standard deviations and used t-tests or ANOVA, where relevant, to explore group differences. Experimental data were analysed using Average Marginal Component Effects (AMCEs) (Hainmueller et al., 2014) to estimate the probability of selecting specific attribute categories, and Marginal Means (MMs) (Leeper et al., 2019) to assess group-level preferences and likelihoods of selection. Respondents with missing information were excluded from analyses unless their data were directly relevant, resulting in variation in sample sizes across questions.

¹ Survey experiments offer a way to assess public opinion by systematically varying certain elements of a question and observing how these changes shape respondents’ answers. This approach makes it possible to identify the influence of specific features—such as wording or the characteristics presented in a scenario—on patterns of response. Their use has grown steadily within migration research (Sobolewska and Lessard-Phillips, 2024).

2.4. Survey respondents' main characteristics

This section provides an overview of the key characteristics of respondents to the I-CLAIM survey in Italy. Supporting tables are presented in the Appendix (Tables A.2–A.4).

As shown in Table A.2, the sample displayed a range of demographic characteristics. The mean age of respondents was 50.8 years (not in the Table), with most (44.5%) respondents in the middle age (40–64) category; 28.4% between 18 and 39, and 27.1% 65 and over. Just over 48% of respondents were men, and close to 52% were women. Just over 2% of respondents reported as being a member of a minority ethnic group. The largest proportion (44.5%) fell within the middle-age category (40–64 years), while 28.4% were aged between 18 and 39, and 27.1% were aged 65 or above. Just over 48% of respondents were men, and close to 52% were women. Just over 2% of respondents reported as being a member of a minority ethnic group.

Most respondents (64.4%) were married or partnered, and the majority resided in urban areas. Geographically, respondents were distributed across the country, with 45.4% living in the North, 20.7% in the Centre, and 34% in the South and Islands.

Moving onto more socio-demographic characteristics (Table A.3), 47.6% of the respondents reported having low levels of education (up to middle school), 37% had medium levels of education (high school diploma), and 15.4% had high levels of education (first university degree or higher).

Approximately 50% respondents were in paid employment. At the same time, 52% reported low household income (up to EUR 24,999 per year), 41.8% reported a middle income (EUR 25,000–59,999), and only 5.9% reported a higher income (EUR 60,000 and above).

In terms of vote choice in the 2022 election, nearly 37% of respondents reported having chosen not to vote. Among those who voted, approximately 25% voted right-wing parties (Fratelli d'Italia 15%, Lega 5.4%, Forza Italia 5%), around 22% voted centre-left parties (Partito Democratico 12%, Verdi-Sinistra 2%, Azione-Italia Viva 6%, Più Europa 2%), and 9.5% reported voting for the Movimento 5 Stelle.

Given the focus of the survey, respondents' connections to migration were also examined (Table A.4). A small proportion (2.5%) reported being born outside Italy, while 10.5% had at least one parent born abroad. Around 9.7% reported having lived abroad for a period, and a majority (57.4%) indicated that they had immigrant friends.

These characteristics are relevant for two main reasons. First, they provide an overview of the composition of the sample. Second, they enable the identification of key groups for comparative analysis in relation to knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration. In this report, particular attention is given to differences across gender (male/female), age groups (18–39; 40–64; 65+), and political affiliation, as indicated by vote choice in the 2022 election: Fratelli d'Italia (in English: Brothers of Italy, acronym: FdI), Partito Democratico (in English: Democratic Party, acronym: PD), Movimento 5 Stelle (in English: 5 Star Movement, acronym: M5S), other parties, and finally those who chose not to vote (acronym: No Vote).

3. Views toward immigration

In addition to demographic characteristics, the analysis incorporates respondents' broader views on immigration and immigrants, as these are likely to shape perceptions of irregular migration (Ipsos, 2019).

At the outset of the survey, respondents were asked to identify the main issues of concern for the country as well as for themselves personally, allowing for an assessment of the salience of immigration as a policy issue.

With regard to the perceived importance of immigration as a concerning issue, 44.6% of respondents indicated that it constituted a top concern for Italy, and 36.4% that it was a top concern for themselves.

Respondents were also asked to evaluate the perceived costs and benefits of migration in two domains: (1) whether immigrants contribute more to, or draw more from, in terms of taxes and services (Figure 1); and (2) whether immigration undermines or enriches the country's cultural life (Figure 2). These questions replicated items from the European Social Survey (Heath et al., 2016) and were measured on a scale from 0 (more negative evaluation) to 10 (more positive evaluation). For analytical purposes, responses were grouped into three categories: negative (0–4), neutral (5), and positive (6–10). Differences across gender, age, and political affiliation were also examined.

As illustrated in Figure 1, just over 38% of respondents expressed a negative view, indicating that immigrants take out more than they contribute. Approximately 35% expressed a positive view, while around 27% adopted a neutral position. While gender differences were minimal, variation was more pronounced across age groups—older respondents tending to hold more negative views—and across political affiliation, with more negative perceptions among Fratelli d'Italia voters, and a significantly more positive outlook expressed by Partito Democratico voters.

Figure 1 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: immigrant take out/put in more (taxes and services). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=978.

With regard to cultural impact, 41% of respondents expressed a negative view, while 43.7% reported a positive evaluation, and 15.3% remained neutral. There were again no significant differences between men and women, despite women having a less positive outlook. Younger respondents had a remarkably more positive view than older age groups. Again, respondents who voted for Fratelli d'Italia exhibited a more negative outlook (65%), compared to 15% of Partito Democratico voters, and 32% of Movimento 5 Stelle voters. Among Partito Democratico voters, 54.2% of respondents thought that immigrants enrich cultural life in Italy.

Figure 2 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: Cultural life undermined/enriched by immigrants. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=1,031.

Taken together, these findings provide important context regarding the composition of the sample and prevailing attitudes toward immigration more broadly. In the following section, we turn to respondents' perceptions of irregular migration and irregular migrants specifically.

4. Main Results

Having outlined the characteristics of the survey respondents, this section presents the findings addressing the report's central research questions:

- What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants?
- What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work?

Each of these questions is examined in a dedicated subsection. For each, results are first presented for the overall sample, followed by an analysis of variation across key respondent groups (gender, age, and political affiliation).

4.1. Knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants

This section examines respondents' knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants. It first considers perceptions of the scale of irregular migration and the level of concern associated with it, before turning to understandings of pathways into irregular status. It then explores knowledge related to employment, including the sectors in which irregular migrants

4.1.1. Scale and level of concern

A significant gap in public knowledge concerns the perceived scale of irregular migration in Italy. To investigate this, respondents were asked to estimate the proportion of irregular migrants within the foreign-born population. Existing estimates for 2023 place this figure at 9.4% (MIRREM, 2024). Based on this, responses were categorised as falling below/on/around the estimate, up to 10% above the estimate, or more than 10% above the estimate (see Figure 3).

The findings indicate a substantial tendency toward overestimation. More than 82% of respondents overestimated the proportion of irregular migrants by more than 10%, while 11.3% reported estimates within 10% above the upper bound. Only 6.7% of respondents provided estimates around or below the expected estimate. Notable variation emerged across age groups, with older respondents more likely to overestimate, and across political affiliation, with Partito Democratico voters showing comparatively lower levels of overestimation.

Figure 3 Perception of the scale of irregular migration in Italy against estimates. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=935.

Respondents were also asked to gauge the extent to which irregular migration constitutes a concern for Italy, using a scale from 0 (not a concern) to 10 (a major concern). Figure 4 presents the proportion of respondents who indicated that irregular migration was a larger concern (e.g., a score over 5 on the scale). Overall, 81.3% of respondents indicated that irregular migration represents a concern for the country. This perception was more pronounced among older respondents and those who voted for Fratelli d'Italia.

Figure 4 Irregular Migration as concern for Italy.
Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=1,047.

4.1.2. *Becoming 'irregular': testing scenarios*

In addition to perceptions of the scale of the population of irregular migrants and the relevance for policy, the survey explored public understandings of how individuals come to hold an irregular status. Respondents were presented with a set of scenarios and asked to assess the likelihood that each would result in irregularity.

These scenarios were informed by previous research on the legal and policy infrastructures of irregularity (Palumbo and Marchetti, 2024) and on media and political narratives in Italy (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025). Prior findings suggest a misalignment between how a migrant can become irregularised in Italy, what we term the infrastructures of irregularity, and how the process is described in media and political narratives. The scenarios included: (1) an individual with an expired student visa; (2) an individual crossing a border without documentation; (3) an individual awaiting a decision on an asylum application; (4) an individual born in Italy to parents without legal residence; (5) an individual hired through a recruitment agency; and (6) a UK national working within the EU.

Analysing responses to these scenarios is particularly relevant in light of I-CLAIM’s work on narrative of irregularisation (Garofalo Geymonat 2025), indicating that, despite the multiple drivers of irregularity, the political and media narrative overwhelming focuses on unauthorised border crossings when talking about irregular migrants, and tends to criminalise asylum seekers portraying them under a negative light.

Table 1 summarises responses across scenarios, indicating the proportion of respondents who considered each scenario likely or unlikely to result in irregularity, as well as the proportion of respondents who declared that they did not know whether the given scenario would lead to irregularity.

Table 1 Scenarios of irregularity

		Likelihood of scenario leading to irregularity		Uncertainty regarding scenario (N=1,077)
		Never/Sometimes	Most/all of the time	
S c e n a r i o s	Crossing border without documentation (N=974)	76.20%	23.80%	8.60%
	Waiting to hear about their asylum claim (N=917)	58.20%	41.80%	14.60%
	Being born in Italy to parents who do not have legal residence status (N=896)	45.50%	54.50%	16.20%
	Being a worker from the UK in the EU (N=974)	25.50%	74.50%	36.90%
	Having an expired student visa (N=835)	25.40%	74.60%	22.40%
	Being hired through a recruitment company (N=682)	21.10%	78.90%	20.20%

Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

The scenarios most frequently associated with irregularity were crossing a border without documentation and awaiting an asylum decision. This aligns with dominant public narratives, despite the fact that asylum seekers awaiting a decision are legally entitled to remain in Italy, and that international legal frameworks, such as the UN Refugee Convention, explicitly state that irregular border crossing should not preclude or negatively impact on the assessment of a person seeking international protection.

Scenarios least frequently associated with irregularity included having an expired student visa and being recruited through an agency. This is noteworthy given that such mechanisms constitute significant pathways into irregularity within the Italian context (Cacciapaglia et al., 2024; Palumbo and Marchetti, 2024).

Looking at the results more closely, in terms of differences among respondent groups, for the asylum claim scenario (Figure 5), we see that middle-age voters do not identify this scenario as often as their younger counterparts. Partito Democratico voters - with more than 66% of respondents saying ‘most/all the time’ and less than 12% undecided - are among the most convinced that waiting for asylum decision may lead to irregularity.

Figure 5 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: waiting to hear about an asylum claim.
Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Similarly, perceptions of irregular border crossings (Figure 6) were strongly shaped by political affiliation. Among Fratelli d'Italia voters, approximately 85% viewed such crossings as leading to irregular status, with minimal uncertainty. Among Partito Democratico voters, this proportion was lower (68%), and uncertainty was higher.

Figure 6 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: crossing a border without documentation.
Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Interestingly, approximately 45% of respondents identified being born in Italy to parents without legal status as a pathway to irregularity, revealing some degree of public awareness of the situation of children both to parents with an irregular status. Differences across gender, age, and political affiliation were limited for this scenario (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: children born to parents without legal residence. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Finally, respondents overwhelmingly considered it unlikely that UK nationals working in the EU would find themselves in an irregular situation (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: UK workers in the EU. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

4.2. Irregular migrant and work: sectors & overall feelings

Given the focus of the I-CLAIM project on labour conditions, the survey also examined perceptions of irregular migration in relation to work/employment. Respondents were asked to identify sectors in which irregular migrants are most likely to be employed and to indicate their level of comfort with encountering irregular migrant workers in different contexts.

Although over 50% of respondents associated employment with legal residence status, they nonetheless identified several sectors where irregular migrants are perceived to work. For male workers, the most frequently mentioned sectors were agriculture, construction, food delivery, and cleaning. For female workers, respondents most often identified cleaning, childcare and eldercare, agriculture, and hospitality. These patterns were largely consistent across respondent groups.

Table 2 Main sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

	First	Second	Third	Fourth
Male	Agriculture	Construction/renovation	Food delivery	Cleaning and other
Female	Cleaning and other	Child/elderly care	Agriculture	Catering and hospitality

In addition to predefined options, respondents could provide open-ended responses. While relatively few did so, those who responded identified additional sectors, including street-based vending (orig. “vu compra”), prostitution (only for female migrants), drug-related activities (orig. “spaccio”), and organised crime (orig. “mafia”, only for male migrants), reflecting both perceptions of informal labour markets and the persistence of criminalising narratives.

To assess social distance, respondents were asked to indicate their level of comfort with having an irregular migrant working in three settings: their home, their workplace, and a shop. Responses were recorded on a scale from 0 (would not mind at all) to 10 (would mind a great deal), with higher values indicating greater social distance (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Social distance indicators. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline Ns=974/941/969.

Overall, levels of social distance were moderate. Respondents expressed low levels of social distance towards irregular migrants working in shops or in their domestic settings (e.g. a mean score around 5). Slightly higher levels of discomfort (“I mind a little”) were reported in relation to irregular migrants working in their workplace.

Notably, respondents consistently reported greater comfort with irregular migrants working in private homes than in workplaces. This pattern reflects the normalisation of employing irregular migrants in private homes for cleaning, babysitting and elderly care in the Italian context (Marchetti and Lashchuk 2025). Indeed, in the context of a rapidly aging society, in the last 20 years the solution to care for the elderly in Italy has de facto become a ‘migrant in the family model’, with very limited support from the public system, therefore largely left to irregular employment (Bettio et al 2006, Garofalo Geymonat et al. 2023, Marchetti et al 2021).

Across all demographic groups social distance or closeness followed the same pattern: more social distance/less social closeness vis-a-vis encountering irregular migrants in the workplace, then in their home, and finally in shops. However, remarkable variation emerged in the levels of social distance/closeness across demographic groups. Higher levels of social distance were observed among men compared to women, among middle-aged respondents relative to both younger and older groups, and among Fratelli d'Italia voters compared to supporters of the Movimento 5 Stelle and, more markedly, the Partito Democratico. Conversely, lower levels of social distance were reported among women, younger respondents, and Partito Democratico voters, many of whom expressed little or no discomfort across all settings.

4.3. Attitudes

Building on the findings regarding knowledge and social distance, this section turns to a more detailed exploration of attitudes toward irregular migrants in the sphere of work, with particular attention to how these attitudes intersect with processes of racialisation and gender. This focus is central to the aims of I-CLAIM, which seeks to understand how public perceptions contribute to broader narratives that shape—and often reinforce—the production of irregularity. To investigate these dimensions, the survey employed a combination of approaches, including experimental techniques. These experiments make it possible to observe how respondents react when specific features of a scenario are varied, offering an unobtrusive way to capture individual preferences on a sensitive topic while minimising bias.

Two experiments are presented here: one examining hiring preferences for irregular migrants, and another assessing perceptions of irregular migrants’ level of integration in Italian society.

4.3.1. Hiring choice

In the hiring experiment, respondents were invited to assess a set of hypothetical candidates applying for a caregiving role for a relative. This occupation was selected because it emerged—both in existing research and in respondents’ own answers—as a key area where irregular migrant workers are commonly employed. Participants evaluated two pairs of applicants, one male and one female, each presented with a set of characteristics and all unable to provide proof of legal residence in Italy, signalling an irregular status. The candidate profiles were designed to vary systematically across several attributes, including country of origin and associated name (see Table A.5 in the Appendix), length of time spent in Italy, whether the applicant had a recommendation, and the location of their family. Figure 10 provides an illustration of the information shown to respondents. Respondents were asked to rate how likely they would be to hire each candidate and to indicate which of the two they would ultimately choose.

Figure 11 Results from hiring choice experiment.
Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,077.

Results from Figure 11 indicate that, when hiring, respondents were less likely to hire candidates from Morocco than from Ukraine. If we break this down by the gender of the candidate, this was the case for male candidates. Respondents were more likely to hire candidates with a longer stay of residence and who were recommended by a friend. Additionally, candidates who were providing for their family based in Italy were more positively evaluated for hiring, especially for female candidates, for whom having family abroad had a negative effect on selection.

It is also useful to examine how individual attributes were viewed across different respondent groups. To do this, we draw on Marginal Means (Leeper et al., 2019), which capture the overall favourability of each attribute, independent of the other characteristics shown. Figures 12–13 present these results. Values positioned to the right of the dotted line indicate that respondents generally preferred that attribute, while those to the left reflect a negative preference. Estimates that cross the reference line suggest no meaningful difference in either direction.

What we can see from the figures is that, in their hiring choices, both male and female respondents expressed a negative preference for the Moroccan candidate, and a positive preference for the Peruvian candidate, with female respondents slightly more positive toward the candidate from Peru. Length of residence mattered more for male compared to female respondents, and both groups indicated a preference for recommendation status (especially female respondents). For both groups, location of family in the country of origin was linked to negative preferences and with positive preferences when family was located in Italy.

Figure 12 Attribute preference by gender of respondents, hiring choice experiment.
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,077.

With regard to the age groups of respondents (Figure 13), most differences in the preferences operated at the level of the origin of respondents. The respondents aged 40-64 show more pronounced preferences compared to both the older and the younger groups: more positive for the candidates from Peru, and more negative for the candidate from Morocco. Older age groups expressed no preference for length of residence and preferences for recommendation status and location of family worked in the expected directions.

Figure 13 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means).
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,077.

Political affiliation further shaped preferences. Fratelli d'Italia voters expressed more polarised attitudes, favouring Ukrainian candidates and disfavoring Moroccan candidates more strongly.

Also noticeable is that Fratelli d'Italia voters did not attribute much importance to length of residence and the recommendation status - while origin really was the only aspect that mattered. Partito Democratico voters were not swayed by length of residence and the location of the family (data points crossing the dotted line). Recommendation status was quite salient for both Movimento 5 Stelle and Partito Democratico voters.

Figure 14 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means).

Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,077.

4.3.2 Perceptions of integration and settlement

The survey also examined respondents' attitudes toward irregular migrants within the context of work through the lens of their perceptions of long-term settlement, or integration, of irregular migrants engaging in work. This dimension is especially relevant given that, despite popular discourses about irregularity focusing mostly on newly-arrived migrants, some irregular migrants have settled in Italy for a number of years. Moreover, exploring perceptions of male irregular migrants—who are frequently subject to more negative public representations—was deemed of relevance.

Respondents were asked to evaluate the level of integration of two hypothetical profiles of male irregular migrants, one from Moldova and one from Senegal, using a scale ranging from 0 (not integrated at all) to 10 (fully integrated). Each profile included a set of randomly assigned attributes deemed to influence evaluations of the level of integration, including reason for migration, language proficiency, religiosity, location of family and friends, and marital status (see Table A.6) Example of what was seen by respondents is shown in Figure 15.

Please read the profile provided and answer the question below it.

Mamadou came to Italy *from Senegal to get an education* but does not have legal residence. He is engaging in work and *does not speak* Italian fluently. *He regularly practices his religion*. His friends are mostly in *Italy*. *He is single*.

On a scale from 0 to 10, how well integrated, if at all, do you think *Mamadou* is in Italian society?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
 Not well integrated at all Very well integrated
 Don't know

Figure 15 Experimental set up for perceptions of integration experiment (varying attributes in italics and blue for reference – see Appendix Table A.6 for details)

The results of the analysis are presented in Figures 16 and 17. As in the previous experiment, coefficients to the right of the reference line indicate a positive effect on perceived integration, while those to the left indicate a negative effect, and data points crossing the dotted line indicating non-significant results.

We begin by examining how each attribute shaped respondents' assessments of integration, first looking at the combined results for both profiles (Figure 16) and then considering how evaluations differed according to the profile's country of origin (Figure 17). Across both profiles, the most influential factors in shaping perceptions of integration were Italian language proficiency and the location of social ties. Individuals who were not fluent in Italian, or who maintained family and friendship networks primarily in their country of origin, were consistently evaluated as less integrated. Conversely, the presence of social ties in Italy was associated with higher levels of perceived integration.

Other attributes had more moderate effects. Religious practice and being married were generally associated with slightly more positive evaluations of integration levels. As a whole, aspects linked to social integration are most relevant (Sobolewska, Galandini, and Lessard-Phillips, 2017). Moreover, the reasons for immigration do not appear to have a significant impact on the evaluation of integration, but we see that 'improving standards' is linked to a slight positive coefficient, the 'education' coefficient is quite close to zero, and 'protection' is linked to a slightly negative coefficient. The Moldovan profile received a slightly higher evaluation compared to the Senegalese one, but not enough to warrant significant differences between the two.

This picture was generally consistent across the origin of the person, with the exception that the location of friends and family led to slightly more negative evaluations of the profiles from Moldova and that being single led to slightly more positive evaluations of integration for profiles from Moldova while it was seen as neutral for profiles from Senegal.

Figure 16 Results from perceptions of integration experiment, all profiles (Average Marginal Effects)
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,015.

Figure 17 Results from perceptions of integration experiment, by origin of profile (Average Marginal Effects).
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,015.

Group-level analyses (Figure 18) indicate that overall female respondents generally assigned higher integration scores than male respondents. This is exemplified by the more positive preferences for both origins, as well as Italian proficiency, having friends and family in Italy, and engaging in religious practice among female respondents.

A difference can be noticed also in the evaluation of the reasons to migrate, where men tend to give a clearly more positive evaluation to ‘improving living standard’, and female respondents tended to have more positive preferences when profiles did not show a reason for migration (and generally more positive, but non-significant, preferences for the ‘education’ and ‘protection’ categories). Overall, however, the pattern of preferences was relatively consistent across attributes.

Figure 18 Attribute preference by gender of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means).
Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,015.

Age differences were more pronounced (Figure 19). First, the youngest respondents (18-39) were generally more positive overall and expressed positive preferences for the Senegalese and Moldovan profile, as opposed to middle-age respondents who slightly preferred the Moldovan over the Senegalese profiles. The youngest group also expressed a positive preference for all reasons for migrating, while only the ‘education’ reason was positively evaluated by the middle-aged group (all the other preferences were more negative and non-significant). Moreover, the youngest group of respondents attributed similar positive preferences to profiles of migrants who were married or single - while middle-age respondents viewed being married as positive in their evaluations of integration. While Italian fluency was seen as positive across all ages, again more positive among younger respondents, non-Italian fluency was not seen as negatively by the younger respondents. Finally, compared to older respondents, respondents aged 18-39 gave a more positive evaluation to the fact of practicing religion.

Figure 19 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means).

Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,015.

Political affiliation also shaped evaluations (Figure 20). Respondents who voted for Fratelli d'Italia were the most negative in their attribute preferences for the evaluation of integration, with all attributes linked to negative (although not always significant) preferences. Instead 5Stars and Partito Democratico voters as well as non-voters expressed some more positive preferences. Language fluency was linked to positive preferences for all respondents aside from Fratelli d'Italia voters. Lack of language fluency was linked to negative preferences for Fratelli d'Italia and non-voters. The presence of family in Italy was seen as a positive attribute by all respondents with the exception of Fratelli d'Italia voters, who viewed having family in the country of origin as negative. With regard to the origin of profiles, while most respondents were generally positive toward both origins, Fratelli d'Italia voters expressed negative preferences for the Senegalese profile (preference was also negative, but just non-significant, for Moldovan profiles). Regarding reasons for migration, Partito Democratico voters were generally more positive toward all reasons aside from education, Movimento 5 Stelle voters and non-voters more positive toward the 'improving standard' reason, and non-voters were more positive when no reason for migration was mentioned. Again, none of these reasons mattered for Fratelli d'Italia voters (preferences were negative but non-significant).

Figure 20 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, perceptions of integration experiment (Marginal Means).
Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,015.

5. Conclusion

This report has provided new empirical insights into how the Italian public understands and perceives irregular migration, with particular attention to work and employment. Several key patterns emerge from the findings, including significant knowledge gaps, the persistence of partial and distorted narratives, the influence of political affiliation and of age in shaping attitudes, and the coexistence of suspicion and pragmatism in attitudes toward irregular migrants.

The findings reveal a striking gap in how well the public understands the notion of irregularity, with knowledge appearing fragmented and unevenly distributed. A substantial majority of respondents overestimated the proportion of irregular migrants within the foreign-born population. While available estimates place this figure at 9.4% of the foreign-born, 82% of respondents provided estimates that exceeded this range by a considerable margin (by 10% more). This tendency was especially pronounced among middle-aged and older respondents, as well as among those who voted for Fratelli d'Italia and Movimento 5 Stelle. However, a large majority of younger respondents (73%) and of voters of the Partito Democratico (62%) also gave a large overestimate of irregular migrants. These findings suggest that public perceptions are shaped less by empirical evidence than by interpretative frameworks circulating in political and media discourse.

Closely related to this is a marked divergence between the policy infrastructures of irregularity and public understandings of how irregular status arises. Respondents readily identified highly visible scenarios—such as unauthorised border crossings and asylum procedures—as pathways to irregularity, yet showed limited awareness of more routine administrative mechanisms, including such as overstaying a student visa or losing lawful residence due to employment changes. This reflects a broader tendency within Italian public discourse to reduce irregular migration to border-related events and asylum, thereby obscuring the structural and bureaucratic dimensions of irregularisation.

At the same time, attitudes toward irregular migrants as workers reveal a degree of ambivalence. Respondents recognised the presence of irregular migrants in key sectors of the Italian economy, including agriculture, construction, cleaning and care work, cleaning, food delivery, and hospitality. In hiring experiments, they demonstrated a degree of pragmatism, favouring candidates with longer residence, strong social recommendations, and family ties in Italy, even in the absence of legal status. However, these preferences were mediated by racialised and gendered hierarchies, with Moroccan candidates consistently evaluated less favourably than those from Peru and Ukraine, and with female candidates more harshly judged for having families in their countries of origin. Stronger negative responses were expressed by middle aged (40-64) and right-leaning respondents.

Perceptions of integration similarly revolved around social markers of belonging, particularly language proficiency and the presence of family and social networks in Italy. Respondents across political and demographic groups associated these characteristics with higher levels of integration, with the exception of Fratelli d'Italia voters for whom they made no difference.

Measures of social distance similarly revealed this ambivalence. Low levels of discomfort were reported in everyday interactions with irregular migrant workers in all contexts. Remarkably, most respondents do not mind having irregular migrants working in their home - which reflects a normalised use of irregular migrant labour in domestic and care work in Italy.

Taken together, these findings suggest that public perceptions of irregular migration in Italy are shaped by what can be understood as an *irregularity assemblage*: a complex interplay of political narratives, legal frameworks, and social imaginaries that define who is considered “irregular” and how such individuals are evaluated. While public knowledge is often partial and uneven across demographic and political lines, attitudes are not uniformly negative. Rather, they reflect a combination of scepticism, pragmatism, and conditional openness, particularly in relation to perceived indicators of integration, proximity and sectoral needs.

6. References

- Abraham, T. (2025) I-Claim Technical Report. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/17701058>.
- Benson, M., Sigona, N. (2024) 'Reimagining, Repositioning, Rebordering: Intersections of the Biopolitical and Geopolitical in the UK's Post-Brexit Migration Regime (and Why It Matters for Migration Research)'. *International Migration Review*, 58(4), 2040-2065.
- Bettio, F., Simonazzi, A., Villa, P. (2006). 'Change in Care Regimes and Female Migration': the 'care drain' in the Mediterranean. *Journal of European Social Policy*, 16(3), 271-285.
- Cacciapaglia, M., Bonizzoni, P., & Ambrosini, M. (2024). *Italy Country Brief on Irregular Migration Policy Context*. MlrreM Report. Krems: University for Continuing Education Krems (Danube University Krems). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12622370>
- Garofalo Geymonat, G. (2025). *The public discourse on migration, irregularity and work in Italy: The intersectionality of narratives in media, civil society and politics*. Country Report. I-CLAIM.
- Garofalo Geymonat, G., S. Marchetti, L. Palumbo (2023) Migrant women workers in Europe: forms of irregularity and conditions of vulnerability in *Ilse van Liempt; Joris Schapendonk; Amalia Campos-Delgado (eds.) Research Handbook on Irregular Migration* Edward Elgar Publishing, pp.215-226.
- Gonzales, R.G., Sigona, N., Franco, M., Papoutsis, A. (2019) *Undocumented migration*, Cambridge: Polity.
- Hainmueller, J., Hopkins, D.J. and Yamamoto, T. (2014) 'Causal Inference in Conjoint Analysis: Understanding Multidimensional Choices via Stated Preference Experiments', *Political Analysis*, 22(1), pp. 1–30.
- Heath, A., Schmidt, P., Green, E.G., Ramos, A., Davidov, E. and Ford, R. (2016) *Attitudes towards immigration and their antecedents*. Topline Results from Round 7 of the European Social Survey. ESS Topline Results Series Issue 7. London.
- Ipsos (2019) *Ciak MigrAction indagine sulla percezione del fenomeno migratorio in Italia* <https://www.ipsos.com/it-it/ciak-migraction-indagine-sulla-percezione-del-fenomeno-migratorio-italia>
- Ipsos (2024) *Perils of perception*. A 30-Country Ipsos Global Advisor Survey <https://www.ipsos.com/sites/default/files/ct/news/documents/2024-11/ipsos-the-perils-of-perception-2024.pdf>
- Leeper, T.J., Hobolt, S.B. and Tilley, J. (2020) 'Measuring Subgroup Preferences in Conjoint Experiments', *Political Analysis*, 28(2), pp. 207–221.
- Lessard-Phillips & L., Sigona, N. (2025). *Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in the UK*. Country Report. I-CLAIM.
- Marchetti, S., and Lashchuk, I. (2025) *Irregularised migrant domestic workers in Naples, Italy*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/15775615>

Marchetti, S. Marchetti S., Cherubini D., and Garofalo. Geymonat, G. (2021), *Global Domestic Workers: Intersectional Inequalities and Struggles for Rights*, Bristol University Press.

MIRREM (2024) *The MirreM Public Data Portal on Irregular Migration Stock*. Available from: <https://irregularmigration.eu/data-portal/>.

Palumbo, L. (2026) *Infrastructures of irregularity and bureaucratic violence affecting migrant people in Italy*, *Rassegna Italiana di Sociologia*, 1, pp. 5-34

Palumbo, L. (2025) *Women migrant workers with precarious legal status in the agricultural sector in Southern Italy*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15833919>

Palumbo, L., Marchetti, S. (2024) *The legal and policy infrastructure of irregularity: Italy*. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/11208940>

Sigona, N. and van Liempt, I. (2025) 'The irregularisation of migration and migrants' irregular condition: an assemblage perspective', IRIS Working Paper Series, no. 50/2025, Birmingham: University of Birmingham. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/17489274>

Sigona, N., Kato, J. & Kuznetsova, I. (2021) 'Migration infrastructures and the production of migrants'irregularity in Japan and the United Kingdom', *Comparative Migration Studies*, 9(31). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-021-00242-4>

Sobolewska, M. and Lessard-Phillips, L. (2024) "Survey experiments in migration research" in: William L. Allen & Carlos Vargas-Silva (ed.), *Handbook of Research Methods in Migration*, Chapter 3, pp. 31–47, Edward Elgar Publishing.

Sobolewska, M., Galandini, S. and Lessard-Phillips, L. (2017) 'The public view of immigrant integration: multidimensional and consensual. Evidence from survey experiments in the UK and the Netherlands', *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 43(1), pp. 58–79. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2016.1248377>

UNICEF 2024 *Così lontani, così vicini. Gli atteggiamenti di adolescenti e giovani nei confronti dei loro pari con background migratorio in Italia*. DOI: <https://www.unicef.it/pubblicazioni/cosi-lontani-cosi-vicini/>

van Liempt, I., Grzymala-Kazłowska, A., Matuszczyk, K., Palumbo, L. (2026). *Immigration Status and Labour Conditions: Migrant workers in Agriculture, Delivery and Logistics, and Domestic and Care Work in Europe*. Sector Report. I-CLAIM. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/18539025>

Appendices

Table A1 Overview of the content of the I-CLAIM survey

Section	Description of question
A. Overall concerns	Top issues facing the country today
	Top issues facing you personally
B. Attitudes and experience toward immigration	Close friends as immigrants (split allocation)
	Whether immigrants take more in or out of society
	Whether cultural like undermined or enriched by immigrants
	Views on immigrants and work
C. Perception of irregular migration/migrants	Percentage of irregular migrants in country
	Whether irregular migration is a concern in country
	Work sector for female irregular migrants
	Work sector for male irregular migrants
	Scenarios of irregularity
D. Attitudes toward irregular migration and work/employment	List experiment on policy deservingness for female cleaner
	Conjoint experiment – <i>female care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Conjoint experiment – <i>male care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Factorial experiment – <i>Perceptions of integration for male irregular migrant 1</i>
	Factorial experiment – <i>Perceptions of integration for male irregular migrant 2</i>
	Social distance indicator – <i>3 scenarios</i>
	E. Further demographics
Religiosity	
Member of ethnic minority group	
Has lived outside of country for over 1 year	

Table A.2: Main Demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Age (N=1,013)	Adult (18-39)	28.4%
	Middle Age (40-64)	44.5%
	Older adults (65+)	27.1%
Gender (N=1,077)	Male	48.1%
	Female	51.9%
Ethnic Minority (N=1,000)	No	97.9%
	Yes	2.1%
Marital Status (N=1,071)	Married, partnership, living as married, in a relationship	64.4%
	Divorced, widowed, separated	13.2%
	Single, other	22.4%
Location (N=1,077)	Urban	50.3%
	Suburban, rural	49.7%
Region (N=1,077)	North west	27.0%
	North east	18.4%
	Centre	20.7%
	South	22.7%
	Islands	11.3%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.3: Socio-demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Education level (N=1,077)	Low	47.6%
	Medium	37.0%
	High	15.4%
Work status (N=1,077)	Working	50.9%
	Not working	49.1%
Household income (N=884)	Low	52.3%
	Medium	41.8%
	High	5.9%
Party voted for in 2023 (N=1,077)	Movimento 5 Stelle	9.5%
	Lega	5.4%
	Forza Italia	5.0%
	Fratelli d'Italia	15.0%
	Partito Democratico	11.7%
	Plus Europe	2.1%
	Azione-Italia Viva	6.1%
	Alleanza Verdi-Sinistra	2.0%
	Abstained	36.6%
	Other	6.6%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.4: Respondents' Links to migration

Characteristic	Categories	%
Country of birth (N=1,072)	Outside of Italy	2.5%
	Italy	97.5%
Immigrant parentage (N=1,064)	None	89.5%
	One parent	4.9%
	Two parents	5.6%
Experience of migration (N=1,063)	No	90.4%
	Yes	9.6%
Has immigrant friends (N=1,062)	None	42.6%
	Yes, several	7.1%
	Yes, a few	50.3%

Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

Table A.5 Attributes for hiring experiment randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN: FEMALE NAME/MALE NAME Two of three chosen for the female and male candidates.	Ukraine: Mariia/ Ivan Morocco: Fatima/Ahmed Peru: Carmen/Carlos
LENGTH OF RESIDENCE One of two.	under a year 5 years
RECOMMENDATION STATUS One of two.	<no recommendation> but comes recommended by a friend
LOCATION OF FAMILY One of two.	Country of origin Survey country

Table A.6 Attributes for integration experiments randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN/NAME One for each profile	Senegal: Mamadou Moldova: Alexandru
REASON FOR MIGRATION One of four.	<no reason stated> to improve his living standards to get an education to seek protection
SURVEY COUNTRY LANGUAGE FLUENCY One of two.	speaks does not speak
RELIGIOSITY One of two.	He regularly practices his religion. <none stated>

LOCATION OF FRIENDS One of two.	From COUNTRY OF ORIGIN From SURVEY COUNTRY
FAMILY STATUS One of two.	He is single He has a family
LOCATION OF FAMILY If has family One of two.	In COUNTRY OF ORIGIN In SURVEY COUNTRY

I-CLAIM Consortium

Utrecht
University

UNIVERSITY OF
BIRMINGHAM

Ca' Foscari
University of Venice
Department of Philosophy
and Cultural Heritage

UNIVERSITY
OF WARSAW

HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO
HELSINGFORS UNIVERSITET
UNIVERSITY OF HELSINKI

Katholische
Hochschule Mainz
Catholic University
of Applied Sciences

THE JOINT COUNCIL
for THE WELFARE
OF IMMIGRANTS

act:onaid
—REALIZZA IL CAMBIAMENTO—

Centrala

ASSOCIATION
FOR LEGAL
INTERVENTION

CONFEDERATION
SYNDICAT
EUROPÉEN
TRADE UNION

Deaconess
Foundation

LEBEN IN DER
LEGALITÄT

Contact info

icclaim@uu.nl

For press inquiries:

I-CLAIM Communications Manager

miriam.mir@ceps.eu

Follow us

www.i-claim.eu

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe